

NEW RECORDS OF APHIDS (HEMIPTERA: APHIDOIDEA)
FROM MADEIRA AND AZORES ARCHIPELAGOSBY ANTÓNIO M. FRANQUINHO AGUIAR, FERNANDO ALBANO ILHARCO,
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ABSTRACT

22 new aphid species are recorded for Madeira Archipelago (Madeira Island: 19, Porto Santo Island: 2, Desertas Islands: 1). These species are *Aloephagus myersi*, *Aphis idaei*, *A. loti*, *A. sambuci*, *Brachyunguis tamaricis*, *Cinara confinis*, *C. cupressi*, *C. fresai*, *Clypeoaphis suaetae*, *Ctenocallis setosus*, *Eriosoma patchiae*, *Greenidea ficicola*, *Hoplocallis pictus*, *Illinoia goldamaryae*, *Phloeomyzus passerinii*, *Pseudacaudella rubida*, *Saltusarius scirpus*, *Sipha maydis*, *Smynthurodes betae*, *Takecallis arundicolens*, *Uroleucon* cf. *nigrocampulanulae*, and *Uroleucon picridis*. Five previously recorded species have spread to new islands in the Archipelago, namely *Aphis solanella* (Selvagens), *Brachycaudus helychrisi* (Selvagens), *Nasonovia ribisnigri* (Selvagens), *Pemphigus bursarius* (Madeira Island) and *Pineus pini* (Porto Santo). For the Azores Archipelago, we add three new records: *Aphis oenotherae* (Pico), *Illinoia lambersi* (São Miguel) and *Neophyllaphis podocarpi* (São Miguel). In the Azores the following species have extended their distribution to new islands: *Aphis craccivora* (São Jorge), *A. fabae* (Pico), *A. hederæ* (Pico), *A. ruborum* (São Jorge), *Cinara pinimariitima* (Pico, São Jorge) and *Macrosiphum rosae* (São Jorge). The status of the species from Madeira referred to in the literature as *Aphis paralioides* is analysed. The total number of aphid species recorded for each of the Macaronesian Archipelagos (Madeira, Azores, Canary Islands, Cape Verde Islands) is given, as is the number of species for each of the 36 islands in these Archipelagos. Currently, 183 aphid species are recorded for the Madeira Archipelago and 151 species for the Azores Archipelago.

Keywords: Aphidoidea, new records, Madeira Archipelago, Porto Santo, Desertas, Selvagens, Azores Archipelago, São Miguel, Pico, Corvo, Flores, Faial, Terceira, Santa Maria, São Jorge, Graciosa, Canary Islands, Cape Verde Islands, Macaronesia

INTRODUCTION

The Aphidoidea of Madeira Island has been particularly well studied, with more than 70 references dealing with this group since the oldest known publication (Tavares, 1903). Besides important contributions like those of Ilharco (1974; 1984), the most recent account for the Madeira Archipelago reported a total of 161 species, most of them from Madeira Island and only one endemic species (Aguiar & Ilharco, 2008).

The knowledge of the Azorean Aphidoidea has also received the attention of recent studies (e.g. Ilharco, 1976; Pita & Ilharco, 2004a; and the latest checklist, Pita & Ilharco, 2010, which record a total of 148 species for the nine islands of the Archipelago).

This paper adds 22 new species for the Madeira Archipelago and three for the Azores, bringing the total to 183 known species for Madeira and 151 for the Azores. We also add data on species that were previously recorded from an island, or islands, in a particular Archipelago but have now extended their distributions to other islands. In the discussion, we present the total number of species for each island in each Macaronesian Archipelago; Madeira (including Selvagens), Azores, Canary Islands and Cape Verde Islands (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. — Map showing the Macaronesian Archipelagos.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

All the specimens studied in this research are deposited in the Collection of the Madeira Agricultural Laboratory (ICLAM), mounted on permanent slides labelled with an alpha-numeric code beginning with the letter 'A'. Slides were observed through a Nikon Optiphot-2 microscope and identified using the dichotomous keys provided by Blackman (2013), Blackman & Eastop (1989; 1994; 2006) and Nieto Nafria *et al.* (2005). Geographical referencing of the collecting sites, when available, is given (in most cases) as Universal Transverse Mercator coordinates using the WGS84 geodetic datum.

RESULTS

New Records from the Madeiran Archipelago

APHIDIDAE

Aphis idaei van der Goot, 1912

New record for Madeira Island and also for Macaronesia. This Eurasian (Heie, 1986), species is already known from mainland Portugal and Spain (Gomez Menor & Nieto Nafria, 1977; Palma & Rei, 1999). Widely distributed in the Palaearctic and Nearctic regions and introduced to the Australian region (Lowe, 1966; Nieto Nafria, *et al.*, 2005).

Aphis idaei (Small European Raspberry Aphid) is able to colonize wild and cultivated raspberries, including loganberry. The colonies feeding at the tips of young shoots cause severe leaf curling, but this aphid is important only as a potential vector of several raspberry viruses, including raspberry vein chlorosis (RVCV) (Alford, 1984; Blackman & Eastop, 1989).

Material Examined: MADEIRA – A878, 5 apterae, ex *Rubus idaeus* (Rosaceae), Feiteira de Cima, Santana, 578m, UTM 324050.22m E, 3629539.79m N, 15.iv.2005.

Aphis loti Kaltenbach, 1862

New record for Madeira and apparently also for Macaronesia as this species is not listed in the most recent checklists for this region (Oromí, Cruz, & Báez, 2010; Pita & Ilharco, 2010; Pérez Hidalgo, Báez & Martín, 2005), although Heie (1986) records having seen *A. loti* material collected in Tenerife. Already known from mainland Portugal, it has a Western Palaearctic distribution, from the Mediterranean (Sicily) north to Norway, west to Spain and east as far as Romania (Nieto Nafria, 2004). Plant hosts include species of *Lotus*, *Astragalus*, *Anthyllis*, *Melilotus* and *Medicago* (Fabaceae). Due to morphological similarities, it is possible that *A. loti* has, in some instances, been misidentified with *A. craccivora*, a common aphid throughout Macaronesia.

Material Examined: MADEIRA – A970, 3 apterae and 1 nymph, ex *Lotus glaucus* (Fabaceae), near Prainha, north of main road, Caniçal, Machico, 82m, UTM 338888.32m E, 3624497.01m N, 24.i.2008.

Aphis sambuci Linnaeus, 1758

New record for the Archipelago of Madeira and Macaronesia, although this species is already known from mainland Portugal. Worldwide it is known from many European countries, North Africa, Palaearctic Asia and Oriental region, the Nearctic region and was introduced to several countries (Argentina, Brazil, Chile) of the Neotropical region (Nieto Nafria *et al.*, 2005).

This aphid builds dense colonies on young stems of the primary host, plants of the genus *Sambucus* (Caprifoliaceae), and host alternation occurs to roots of secondary hosts, particularly belonging to the Caryophyllaceae, but also many others in several plant families (Nieto Nafria *et al.*, 2005; Blackman, 2013).

Material Examined: MADEIRA – A1086, 1 alata and 5 nymphs, ex *Sambucus lanceolata* (Caprifoliaceae), Quinta do Santo da Serra, Machico, 690m, 3.vii.2013.

Brachyunguis tamaricis (Lichtenstein, 1885)

New record for the Madeiran Archipelago. This species is already known from Macaronesia and from mainland Portugal. Recorded for the Azores (Santa Maria Island) by Pita & Ilharco (1997) and for the Canary islands by Nieto Nafría, Mier Durante & Carnero Hernández (1977); unknown in the Cape Verde islands.

These are very small and inconspicuous greenish-grey aphids that are difficult to observe on the host plant twigs. This species is monoecious and holocyclic, feeding on various *Tamarix* spp. (Tamaricaceae) and its world distribution includes central and southern Europe, including the Balearic Islands, Corsica, Sardinia Sicily and Malta, North Africa, southwest and Central Asia east to Pakistan (Blackman & Eastop, 1994).

Material Examined: Porto Santo – A1034, 12 apterae, ex *Tamarix gallica* (Tamaricaceae), Calheta, 8m, UTM 371209m E, 3654877m N, 29.vii.2012.

Clypeoaphis suaedae (Mimeur, 1934)

New record for Madeira Island. Already recorded from Macaronesia: Cape Verde (Sal Island) (van Harten, 1993; Pérez Hidalgo, Báez & Martín, 2005). Absent from mainland Portugal. Recorded from Spain, France, Sicily, the Netherlands, British Isles, Kazakhstan, Iran, Yemen, Pakistan, Morocco, Algeria and Egypt (Shaposhnikov, 1964; Barbagallo & Stroyan, 1982; Remaudière, Nieto Nafría & Mier Durante, 1986; van Harten, Ilharco & Prinsen, 1994). In addition to the nominotypical subspecies, *C. suaedae* ssp. *suaedicola* Hille Ris Lambers is recorded from the British Isles, France and the Netherlands.

Within its distributional range, this aphid has been collected on several different species of *Suaeda* Forssk. ex J.F. Gmelin, plants generally associated with drier halophile coastal ecosystems. Genus *Clypeoaphis* Soliman is easily recognized by its highly developed clypeus.

Material Examined: MADEIRA - A862, 5 apterae, ex *Suaeda vera* (Chenopodiaceae), near Marconi installation, Caniçal, Machico, 135m, UTM 340123.23m E, 3624707.73m N, 29.i.2004.

Illinoia goldamaryae (Knowlton, 1938)

New record for Madeira Island. Already recorded from Macaronesia: Azores (São Miguel Island) (Pita & Ilharco, 2005). Known from mainland Portugal since 2003 (Rodrigues, 2004; Rodrigues *et al.*, 2006). A typically Nearctic species in origin (Footitt & Maw, 1997) and introduced to the Neotropical region (Panama, Peru), and the Western Palaearctic (British Isles, Portugal, Slovenia, Tunisia) (Boukhris-Bouhachem *et al.*, 2007; Hrzič, 1996; Nieto Nafría, 2004).

Known food plants of this aphid include several genera of Asteraceae (*Aster*, *Erigeron*, *Solidago*).

Material Examined: MADEIRA – A811, 1 alata, ex unidentified Poaceae, Montado do Sabugal, Fajã da Nogueira, Santana, 854m, UTM 320557.33m E, 3624743.25m N, 14.v.2002; A1062, 2 apterae, ex. *Conyza* sp. (Asteraceae), Ribeiro Frio, 26.x.2011, M. Moreira leg.

***Pseudacaudella rubida* (Börner, 1939)**

New record for Madeira. Already known from several islands of the Azores Archipelago (Pita & Ilharco, 2005). Absent from mainland Portugal, the Canary and Cape Verde Archipelagos. At a global level *P. rubida*'s distribution includes the Nearctic region, Neotropical region (Panama and Brazil) (Quirós, Remaudière & Nieto Nafria, 2009) and the Western Palaearctic (British Isles, Scandinavia, Central Europe, Spain, Italy and Central Russia) (Nieto Nafria, 2004).

Although the only specimen was collected from a pan trap, this species seems to live on mosses (Bryophyta). According to Heie (1991), *P. rubida* is anholocyclic and feeds primarily on *Pleurozium schreberi* and *Scleropodium purum*, mosses that also exist in Madeira (Sérgio *et al.*, 2008).

Material Examined: MADEIRA – A623, 1 alata, ex Moericke pan trap, Pico, Santana, 416m, UTM 323391.76m E, 3631571.16m N, 6.v.1997.

***Uroleucon cf. nigrocampanulae* (Theobald, 1928)**

The identity of this species is still uncertain due to the few specimens available for study. Although the apterae show some morphological differences from typical *U. nigrocampanulae*, this will at least constitute a new record for Madeira, the whole of Macaronesia and mainland Portugal.

It should be noted that Meneses de Sequeira *et al.* (2007) recently described the host plant *Musschia isambertoii* from the Deserta Grande, on observation of two very small and localised colonies. This is the third species in the endemic genus *Musschia* Dum., the other two live exclusively in Madeira Island.

Material Examined: DESERTA GRANDE – A767, 2 apterae, ex *Musschia isambertoii* (Campanulaceae), Porto das Moças, Deserta Grande, 5m, UTM 357197.84m E, 02277.26m N, 25.vi.2001.

***Uroleucon picridis* (Fabricius, 1775)**

Known from the Canary Islands and mainland Portugal, previously also recorded for Madeira but removed from the list by Aguiar & Ilharco (2001) as a misidentification of *Uroleucon mieraee*. According to Tizado Morales & Nieto Nafria (1994) both *U. picridis* and *U. mieraee* can be separated by the absolute length of the apical rostral segment (RIV+V). The key these authors provide (p. 1260) runs directly to *U. picridis* for values of this parameter greater than 256µm. However, recently collected material (see below), showed that 5 specimens had values of RIV+V greater than 256µm (266 ± 4µm). Although the 4 specimens of sample A1059 had values of RIV+V less than 256µm (248 ± 9µm), the

discriminant value D calculated for these specimens is greater than 64.81, which according to the aforementioned authors indicates that it is *U. picridis*. This allows us to conclude that both species are present on Madeira.

Material Examined: MADEIRA – A1057, 3 apterae, 1 alata, ex *Helminthotheca echioides* (Asteraceae), Faial, Santana, 7.vii.2011; A1058, 2 apterae attended by *Lasius grandis* workers, ex *Helminthotheca echioides* (Asteraceae), Cabo Girão, Câmara de Lobos, 29.vii.2011; A1059, 4 apterae, ex *Helminthotheca echioides* (Asteraceae), Santa, Porto Moniz, 24.xi.2011; A1064, 2 apterae attended by *Lasius grandis* workers, ex *Sonchus* sp. (Asteraceae), Caniçal, Machico, 18.viii.2012; A1065, 3 apterae, ex *Helminthotheca echioides* (Asteraceae), Posto Florestal, Santa, Porto Moniz, 29.vi.2012; A1066, 1 aptera, 2 alatae, ex *Sonchus* sp. (Asteraceae), Ribeira da Janela, Porto Moniz, 7.ix.2012; A1067, 2 apterae, 1 alata, ex *Helminthotheca echioides* (Asteraceae), Santa, Porto Moniz, 13.ix.2012. All samples: *M. Moreira* leg.

DREPANOSIPHIDAE

Hoplocallis pictus (Ferrari, 1872)

New record for the Madeira Archipelago of this monoecious holocyclic species. Known from mainland Portugal; in Macaronesia, it was only known from the Azores (Pita & Ilharco, 1997). According to Blackman & Eastop (1994), *H. pictus* can be found on the undersides of *Quercus* spp. leaves throughout the Mediterranean area and in southwest Asia and India. Introduced into South Africa and South America (Argentina, Chile).

Material Examined: PORTO SANTO – A1035, 1 alata, 1 aptera, 4 nymphs, ex *Quercus ilex*, (Fagaceae), Vila Baleira, Largo do Pelourinho, 19m, UTM 375343m E, 3658623m N, 30.vii.2012.

Phloeomyzus passerinii (Signoret, 1875)

New record for Madeira island. Already recorded in Macaronesia from São Miguel Island (Azores) (Pita & Ilharco, 2005). Also known from mainland Portugal (Ilharco, 1979). It is a species with an extensive distribution worldwide, including Europe, North Africa, many regions of Asia, USA (Maine) and several South American countries (Blackman & Eastop, 1994).

More material will have to be collected in Madeira to establish if the alatae sexuales are present as well as the parthenogenetic anholocyclic apterae.

Material Examined: MADEIRA – A869, 3 apterae, ex *Populus alba* (Salicaceae), Pinheiro, Serra de Água, 370m, UTM 309357.58m E, 3622323.04m N, 29.vii.2004; A985, 3 apterae, ex *Populus alba* (Salicaceae), Pinheiro, Serra de Água, 363m, UTM 309343.80m E, 3622307.98m N, 12.viii.2004.

Sipha maydis (Passerini, 1860)

This is the first record of this species for the whole of Macaronesia, although another species of *Sipha* Passerini, (*S. flava* (Forbes)) is recorded from the Azores Islands (Pita & Ilharco, 2004a; 2005). The present distribution of this species is extensive and includes almost the whole of Europe (including mainland Portugal), and the following regions:

Afrotropical, Eastern Palaearctic, Near East, Neotropical, North Africa and Oriental (Nieto Nafria, 2004).

Many authors consider the genus *Rungisia* Mimeur, 1933, a subgenus of *Sipha* Passerini, 1860. Nevertheless, *S. maydis* is recorded for mainland Portugal as *Rungisia maydis* (Ilharco, 1973).

Most likely a recent introduction, this species feeds exclusively on Poaceae, including all the economically important cereals in drier climates.

Material Examined: MADEIRA – A891, 5 alate and 8 apterae, ex. unidentified Poaceae, Gernel, Ilha, Santana, 380m, UTM 321303.76m E, 3631554.32m N, 25.viii.2005; A999, 1 alata, 4 apterae, ex. unidentified Poaceae, football installation near Camacha, Santa Cruz, 673m, UTM 326334m E, 3616382m N, *Marta Moreira* leg., 8.vii.2010; A1000, 1 alata, 2 apterae, 2 nymphs, ex. *Avena* sp. (Poaceae), football installation near Camacha, Santa Cruz, 673m, UTM 326334m E, 3616382m N, *Marta Moreira* leg., 8.vii.2010.

***Saltusaphis scirpus* Theobald, 1915**

New record for Madeira Island. Already recorded in Macaronesia from Faial, Pico, São Miguel and Santa Maria Islands (Azores) (Pita & Ilharco, 2004a; 2005), but not recorded from mainland Portugal. Although described from Egypt and recorded from several other African countries, down to South Africa (Heie, 1975), this species has an extensive distribution worldwide: European, Middle Eastern and Oriental regions. It was introduced to South America (Ortego *et al.*, 2006); its presence, however, in North America is now considered dubious (Footitt *et al.*, 2006).

All Madeiran material was collected from pitfall traps, which thus excluded any association with a host plant. Outside Madeira, the preferred host plants belong to the Cyperaceae (*Cyperus*, *Carex*) and to a lesser extent Juncaceae. The Cyperaceae have at least 26 species in Madeira, most of them native, and this will surely guarantee the survival of this species in the wild.

Material Examined: MADEIRA – A856, 1 aptera, ex. pitfall trap, Centro de Fomento da Bananicultura, Lugar de Baixo, Ponta do Sol, 8m, UTM 304691.17m E, 3617384.06m N, 23.xi.2003; A859, 1 alata, pitfall trap, Centro de Fomento da Bananicultura, Lugar de Baixo, Ponta do Sol, 8m, UTM 304691.17m E, 3617384.06m N, 21.i.2004; A860, 1 aptera, ex. pitfall trap, Centro de Fomento da Bananicultura, Lugar de Baixo, Ponta do Sol, 8m, UTM 304691.17m E, 3617384.06m N, 3.ii.2004; A865, 1 aptera, ex. pitfall trap, Centro de Fomento da Bananicultura, Lugar de Baixo, Ponta do Sol, 8m, UTM 304691.17m E, 3617384.06m N, 16.iii.2004; A866, 1 aptera, ex. pitfall trap, Centro de Fomento da Bananicultura, Lugar de Baixo, Ponta do Sol, 8m, UTM 304691.17m E, 3617384.06m N, 24.iii.2004.

***Takecallis arundicolens* (Clarke, 1903)**

This species was previously unknown from the Macaronesia, but already recorded from mainland Portugal. All four species of *Takecallis* Matsumura live on bamboos. The distribution range of *T. arundicolens* includes China, Japan and Korea, and it was introduced to Europe and California (Blackman & Eastop, 1994). This is the second species of the genus *Takecallis* recorded for Madeira (the first was *T. arundinariae*) and

both were probably introduced with ornamental bamboos. Of the bamboos where both *Takecallis* species were collected, *Pseudosasa japonica* is the most common, medium-sized bamboo in Madeira (Vieira, 2002).

Material Examined: MADEIRA – A960, 5 alate and 1 nymph, ex *Pseudosasa japonica* (Poaceae), São Jorge, Santana, 170m, UTM 322033.00m E, 3634406.00m N, 21.vi.2007; A961, 4 alate, ex *Pseudosasa japonica* (Poaceae), São Jorge, Santana, 159m, UTM 321996.00m E, 3634437.00m N, 21.vi.2007; A974, 5 alate, 1 aptera, 1 nymph, ex *Pseudosasa japonica* (Poaceae), Lombo Antão Alves, Santana, 439m, UTM 322256m E, 3631367m N, 12.vii.2007.

***Greenidea ficicola* Takahashi, 1921**

New record for Madeira Island and also for Macaronesia, but unknown from mainland Portugal. This species is widely distributed in the Eastern Palaearctic (from Eastern Siberia to Japan), Oriental Region (from India to the Philippines, and south to Java and Sumatra) and Australia. In the last two decades, this eminently Asiatic species has been spreading to the western hemisphere. Recently it was introduced to Africa (1992), the USA (2002), Brazil (2003), southern Italy (2005), southern Spain (2005), Peru & Chile (2006), Tunisia (2007) and Malta (2008) (Rubin de Celis, Ortiz & Barletta, 2006; Ben Halima-Kamel, 2009; Bella *et al.*, 2009; Sousa-Silva, Brombal, & Ilharco, 2005).

Although able to feed on several plant families in its native range, this species prefers species of ornamental *Ficus* L. (Moraceae), including the cultivated Mediterranean fig tree, *F. carica* L. It was probably introduced to Madeira via ornamental plant trade. Bella *et al.* (2009) speculate that as this is a thermophilous anholocyclic species, its spread to the western hemisphere may be favoured by global warming.

Material Examined: MADEIRA – A965, 4 apterae, ex *Ficus benjamina* (Moraceae), Montanha, São Gonçalo, Funchal, 231m, UTM 324179.43m E, 3613672.95m N, 19.viii.2007; A966, 3 apterae, ex *Ficus benjamina* (Moraceae), Rua Dr Pita, Funchal, 186m, UTM 318639.04m E, 3613861.77m N, 23.viii.2007; A1061, 4 apterae, ex unidentified plant, Campus da Universidade da Madeira, Penteada, Funchal, 20.vii.2011, *M. Khadem* leg.

LACHNIDAE

***Cinara confinis* (Koch, 1856)**

New record for Madeira Island and Macaronesia. Widespread in the Palaearctic region (most of Europe, including mainland Portugal, Siberia, Central Asia), Oriental region (Pakistan, India). Introduced in the Nearctic region (Canada, western USA) and Neotropical region (Argentina). Absent from the Afrotropical and Australian regions (Blackman & Eastop, 1994; Nieto Nafria, 2004).

Develops colonies on trunk, branches and twigs of *Abies* spp. In climates with mild winters like Madeira, it is anholocyclic without oviparae and alate males. The sample studied was collected in an urban area, on an unidentified (probably imported) *Abies* sp. Andrada (1990) mentions the planting of 4500 firs of three species (*Abies nobilis*,

A. nordmanniana and *A. pectinata*) between 1952 and 1973 for reforestation purposes in the Poiso perimeter, near Funchal. These colonies of exotic conifers will provide the food source for *C. confinis* to expand its distribution in the island.

Material Examined: MADEIRA – A745, 4 apterae, ex *Abies* sp., Caminho Dr. Barreto, São Martinho, Funchal, 214m, UTM 318495.62m E, 3614576.71m N, 23.v.2001.

Cinara cupressi (Buckton, 1881)

The cypress aphid is a new record for Madeira and also for Macaronesia, but already known from the Portuguese mainland. Although of probable Nearctic origin, *C. cupressi* has an extensive worldwide distribution that includes the following regions: Europe, Afrotropical, North Africa, Near East, Eastern Palaearctic, Nearctic, Neotropical, Oriental and Australian (Nieto Nafria, 2004). It was considered as one of the top 100 of the world's worst invasive alien species (Lowe *et al.*, 2000). Recent introductions to Africa (Malawi) in 1986 (Ciesla, 1991) and Brazil in 2000 (Sousa-Silva & Ilharco, 2001) illustrate the continuing world dispersion of this pest.

According to Blackman & Eastop (1994), the most common hosts for *C. cupressi* are *Cupressus* spp. but it can feed on other Cupressaceae. Oviparae and alate males are known in Europe (October), but anholocyclic manifests in regions with milder winters, which should be the case of Madeira.

Material Examined: MADEIRA – A975, 5 apterae, ex *Cupressus lusitanica*, Quinta do Bom Sucesso, Funchal, 314m, UTM 322598.95m E, 3615270.95m N, 31.x.2007.

Cinara fresai Blanchard, 1939

New record for Madeira and also Macaronesia, absent from mainland Portugal. This anholocyclic species has according to Blackman & Eastop (1994) a remarkably disjunctive distribution: England, Wales, Spain, Israel, USA, Central and South America, Australia, New Zealand, Japan, Korea, Hawaii (Beardsley, 1979), and more recently Turkey (Tuatay, 1999) and Poland (Durak, 2012). Although usually commoner on *Juniperus* and *Cupressus* spp., *C. fresai* was also observed on *Cryptomeria japonica*.

Material Examined: MADEIRA – A1060, 1 aptera, ex *Cryptomeria japonica* (Taxodiaceae), Encumeada, São Vicente, 27.v.2012, M. Moreira leg.

Ctenocallis setosus (Kaltenbach, 1846)

New record for Madeira Island and Macaronesia. Absent from mainland Portugal. Known from many European countries, from Scandinavia to the Mediterranean: Denmark, British Isles, the Netherlands, Germany, Poland, Italy, Romania, Greece, Sicily, and also in North Africa: Tunisia (Boukhris-Bouhachem *et al.*, 2007; Nieto Nafria, 2004; Tsitsipis *et al.*, 2007). Introduced to Canada and USA.

C. setosus feeds on brooms, especially *Cytisus scoparius*, common broom, native to western and central Europe. This broom species was

introduced (as an ornamental) to the USA where it became naturalised, and with it probably came *C. setosus*. The alatae collected in Madeira are obviously vagrants as they do not feed on Passifloraceae, although *C. scoparius* is very common on the island from sea level to 1400m.

Material Examined: MADEIRA – A781, [CAEAN6779] 2 alate, ex beatings on *Passiflora edulis* (Passifloraceae), Ribeira Funda, São Jorge, Santana, 293m, UTM 321641.54m E, 3633935.34m N, 7.vii.2001.

PEMPHIGIDAE

Aloephagus myersi Essig, 1950

New record for Macaronesia and recently identified in mainland Portugal on a sample deposited in the collection of the Estação Agronómica Nacional, Oeiras with the number 3072, collected at the Jardim Botânico da Faculdade de Ciências in Lisbon, 16.viii.1979 by A. van Harten on *Aloe arborescens*. The aloe aphid is an Afrotropical species of sub-Saharan origin. It has spread to other regions including the Palaearctic region (Great Britain, France, Spain, Italy and Sicily), Australian region (Australia) and Nearctic region (Canada, United States). Recent introductions have been recorded for Japan (Sano & Matsumoto, 2005), Tunisia (Boukhis-Bouhachem *et al.*, 2007) and Greece (Tsitsipis *et al.*, 2007).

Known hosts include plants belonging to *Aloe*, *Gasteria* and *Haworthia* (Aloaceae), where the aphids live in the bases of leaves. Blackman & Eastop (1989) state that it probably alternates to *Pistacia* in Africa, and is anholocyclic elsewhere.

Material Examined: MADEIRA – A997, 6 apterae, ex. *Aloe vera* (Aloaceae), Zona Franca Industrial, Caniçal, 64m, 32.742239° N, 16.736409° W, 8.vii.2011.

Eriosoma patchiae (Börner & Blunck, 1916)

This is the first record of this Eurasian species for the whole of Macaronesia. Absent from the Iberian Peninsula, its presence in southern Europe is only known from Sicily and it remains unrecorded in France (Barbagallo & Stroyan, 1982; Heie, 1980).

E. patchiae is holocyclic on *Ulmus* spp. where it forms galls on the leaves of young growth and for a secondary host colonizes the roots of Asteraceae, mainly of the genus *Senecio* and *Cineraria* (Blackman & Eastop, 1994). As there are no *Ulmus* spp. recorded from Madeira (Hansen & Sunding, 1993; Jardim & Sequeira, 2008), *E. patchiae* must be exclusively anholocyclic on the roots of Asteraceae in Madeira.

Material Examined: MADEIRA – A873, 1 alata, ex *Delairea odorata* (= *Senecio mikanioides*) (Asteraceae), Pinheiro, Serra de Água, 368m, UTM 309390.07m E, 3622330.84m N, 25.xi.2004.

Smynthurodes betae Westwood, 1849

New record for Madeira Island. Already recorded in Macaronesia from Tenerife Island (Canary Islands) (Oromí, Cruz & Báez, 2010), and also from mainland Portugal. According to Blackman & Eastop (1989), this

species has a worldwide distribution on secondary hosts. As the primary hosts, *Pistacia* spp., are not recorded from Madeira, *S. betae* must be colonizing exclusively the roots of many Asteraceae, Fabaceae and Solanaceae, families to which the many secondary hosts recorded for this aphid belong.

Material Examined: MADEIRA – A967, 3 apterae and 2 alate ex roots and tubers of *Solanum tuberosum* (Solanaceae), Santo António, Funchal, 124m, UTM 319666.03m E, 3614740.76m N, 03.iv.2008.

Species that have extended their distribution in the Madeira Archipelago

ADELGIDAE

Pineus pini (Macquart, 1819)

New record for Porto Santo Island. Already recorded for Madeira Island on *Pinus sylvestris* (Aguiar, Pita & Ilharco, 1995). This adelgid, which is known from mainland Portugal, exists in all the Macaronesian Archipelagos except Cape Verde.

Material Examined: PORTO SANTO – A964, 8 apterae, ex *Pinus halepensis* (Pinaceae), Parque Florestal dos Salões, Porto Santo, 49m, UTM 375320.50m E, 3659543.73m N, 9.iii.2007.

APHIDIDAE

Aphis solanella Theobald, 1914

New record for the Selvagens Islands. This is an introduced, widespread species in the whole of Macaronesia and mainland Portugal. In the Madeira Archipelago it has so far only been recorded for the inhabited islands of Madeira and Porto Santo (Aguiar & Ilharco, 2008).

Material Examined: SELVAGENS ISLANDS – A915, 5 apterae, attended by ants *Monomorium subopacum*, ex *Solanum nigrum* (Solanaceae), Selvagem Grande, 20m above water tank (end of valley), 25.v.2006, *Rui Pereira* leg.; A916, 3 nymphs, ex *Solanum nigrum* (Solanaceae), Selvagem Grande, 20m above water tank (end of valley), 25.v.2006, leg. *Rui Pereira*; A922, 1 aptera, ex *Solanum nigrum* (Solanaceae), Selvagem Grande, Fonte, 18.v.2006, *Rui Pereira* leg.

Brachycaudus helichrysi (Kaltenbach, 1843)

A very common aphid species throughout Macaronesia, but until now unknown in the Selvagens Islands (Aguiar & Ilharco, 2008). It is also known from mainland Portugal.

Material Examined: SELVAGENS ISLANDS – A919, 1 aptera, ex *Lycopersicon esculentum* (Solanaceae), Centro do Vale, Selvagem Grande, 19.v.2006, *R. Pereira* leg.; A1002, 1 alata, pitfall trap, Selvagem Grande, 10.iii.2005, *I. Silva* & *S. Correia* leg.

Nasonovia ribisnigri (Mosley, 1841)

Already known from mainland Portugal and all the Macaronesian Archipelagos except Cape Verde, this is the first record of this species for the Selvagens Islands: identified from a single alata collected on a window pane of the Natural Park shelter. From its secondary hosts mentioned in Blackman & Eastop (2006), one can speculate that such species as *Crepis*

divaricata, *Nicotiana glauca* and *N. tabacum*, which are present in the Selvagem Grande, could be used as host plants.

Material Examined: SELVAGENS ISLANDS – A917, 1 alata, ex. window pane of shelter, Selvagem Grande, 11.v.2006, *J. Nieto Nafria* det., *R. Pereira* leg.

PEMPHIGIDAE

Pemphigus bursarius (Linnaeus, 1758)

New record for Madeira Island. Already recorded for Deserta Grande Island in the Madeiran Archipelago on the roots of a *Tolpis fruticosa* seedling (Ilharco, 1984). In Macaronesia, it is also recorded from the Azores; it is, however, absent from the Canary Islands and Cape Verde. It is present in mainland Portugal.

Material Examined: MADEIRA – A611, 1 aptera, ex. roots of unidentified Poaceae, Paul da Serra, Arco da Calheta, 1409m, UTM 302627m E, 3625966m N, 14.v.1997; A742, 1 alata vagrant, ex *Leucadendron* sp. (Proteaceae), Santo da Serra, Santa Cruz, 700m, UTM 330226.03m E, 3621763.96m N, 19.x.2000.

Taxonomic note

Aphis cf. *hillerislambersi* Nieto Nafria & Mier Durante, 1976 (as *Aphis paralius* Hille Ris Lambers, nomen nudum, Auct.)

This species is relatively common on its host, the Madeira Spurge (*Euphorbia piscatoria*), an endemic and abundant coastal succulent. In previous records for Madeira it has been named as *Aphis paralius* (Ilharco, 1974; 1984; 1986; Aguiar, Pita & Ilharco, 1995; Pita & Ilharco, 2004b; Aguiar & Ilharco, 2008).

According to Blackman & Eastop (2006), and based on the study of material deposited in the Natural History Museum, London (BMNH), they consider it to be *Aphis hillerislambersi*, a Mediterranean-Macaronesian species of Palaearctic origin. Its known distribution includes: Spain, France, Italy, Yugoslavia and Turkey. In Macaronesia, in addition to Madeira, it is known from the Canary Islands.

Careful measurement of apterae collected on Madeira and compared with the type specimen measurements made available by Nieto & Mier (1976) and Nieto Nafria *et al.* (2005) shows some similarity of the Madeira material with that of *A. hillerislambersi* (Table 1). However, there is a discrepancy between the SIPH/RIV+V ratio provided by Nieto & Mier (1976) and the one obtained by us. It is also apparent that the apterae from Madeira have a higher number of caudal setae. These discrepancies (in bold type) could indicate that we are dealing with a different, but close related, species. We will need to measure sufficient alatae (the studied material only contained one) before considering the possibility of this being an undescribed species.

Material Examined: MADEIRA – A376, 7 apterae, 4 nymphs, ex. *Euphorbia piscatoria* (Euphorbiaceae), descent to Porto do Pesqueiro, Ponta do Pargo, Calheta, 100m, UTM 289291m E, 3631614m N, 23.iv.1994; A511, 1 aptera, 11 nymphs, ex. *Euphorbia piscatoria* (Euphorbiaceae), miradouro, Ribeira Brava, 95m, UTM 306893.47m E, 3617454.52m N,

15.xi.1994 (attended by ants: *Plagiolepis schmitzii*); A602, 1 alata, 43 apterae, 276 nymphs, ex. *Euphorbia piscatoria* (Euphorbiaceae), miradouro, Ribeira Brava, 87m, UTM 306524m E, 3616510m N, 11.iii.1997 (attended by ants: *P. schmitzii*); A787, 3 apterae, ex. *Euphorbia piscatoria* (Euphorbiaceae), road from Paul do Mar to Fajã da Ovelha, Calheta, 283m, UTM 290987m E, 3627727m N, 29.xi.2001.

TABLE 1.— COMPARISON OF MEASURED *APHIS* CF. *HILLERISLAMBERSI* APTERAE FROM MADEIRA AGAINST PUBLISHED MORPHOMETRIC PARAMETERS OF TYPE SPECIMENS

Parameters	Nieto Nafria & Mier, 1976	Nieto Nafria et al., 2005	Madeiran N = 23
BL (mm)	1.34–2.00		1.65 ± 0.24
ANT/BL	0.42–0.68	0.40–0.70	0.52 ± 0.05
ANT III/ANT PT	1.33–2.75 (1.50–2.30)		1.70 ± 0.17
ANT PT/BASE	0.88–1.53 (1.00–1.30)	0.90–1.50	1.11 ± 0.09
RIV+V/HT II	0.75–1.00	0.70–1.00	0.91 ± 0.04
SIPH/RIV+V	0.87–1.67 (1.30)		0.66 ± 0.09
SIPH/BL	0.03–0.08		0.04 ± 0.01
SIPH/CAUDA	0.4–0.7	0.4–0.7	0.45 ± 0.04
CAUDA/SIPH	1.81–3.00 (1.95–2.60)		2.22 ± 0.21
CAUDA L/CAUDA BW		1.20–2.00	1.59 ± 0.18
CAUDA BW/ CAUDAL	0.50–0.80		0.64 ± 0.08
ANT III setae (µm)	12–16	10–16	13.64 ± 2.38
ANT III s/BASE ANTHI	0.6–0.9	0.6–0.9	0.67 ± 0.15
RIV+V acc. setae (µm)		25–40	40.92 ± 4.94
HF ventral setae (µm)	23–39	18–39	32.37 ± 5.13
TIII–IV dors. setae (µm)	16–23		16.41 ± 2.41
TVII dors. setae	4–6		3.91 ± 0.51
TVIII dors. setae	2–4		2.04 ± 0.21
TVIII dors. setae (µm)	19–27		17.63 ± 4.48
GP ant. setae	2 (3–4)		3.17 ± 0.65
GP post. setae	9–18 (12–15)		9.83 ± 1.67
HF ds/TF sut.		0.6–1.0	0.56 ± 0.06
CAUDA setae	9–11 (7–12)	7–12	14.83 ± 2.04

Key: BL – body length; ANT/BL – antenna, body length ratio; ANT III/ANT PT – antenna third segment, processus terminalis ratio; ANT PT/BASE – processus terminalis, base ratio; RIV+V/HT II – fourth plus fifth rostrum segments, second hind tarsus ratio; SIPH/RIV+V – siphunculus length, fourth plus fifth rostrum segments ratio; SIPH/BL – siphunculus length, body length ratio; SIPH/CAUDA – siphunculus length, cauda length ratio (and vice-versa); CAUDA L/CAUDA BW – cauda length, cauda base width ratio (and vice-versa); ANT III setae – length of largest seta on third antennal segment; ANT III s/BASE ANT III – length of largest seta on third antennal segment, base width of third antennal segment ratio; RIV+V acc. setae – length of largest accessory seta present on fourth plus fifth rostrum segments; HF ventral setae – length of largest ventral seta on hind femur; T III–IV dors. setae – length of largest dorsal seta on tergites III and IV; T VII dors. setae – number of dorsal setae on tergite VII; T VIII dors. setae – number of dorsal setae on tergite VIII; T VIII dors. setae – length of largest dorsal setae on tergite VIII; GP ant. setae – number of genital plate anterior setae; GP post. setae – number of genital plate posterior setae; HF ds/TF sut. – length of largest hind femur dorsal seta, trochanter-femoral suture ratio; CAUDA setae – number of caudal setae.

New records for the Azores Archipelago

APHIDIDAE

Aphis oenotherae Oestlund, 1887

This Nearctic species constitutes a new record for Macaronesia and is already known from mainland Portugal. It was introduced to Europe, Hawaii, Japan, Korea and Australia. According to Blackman & Eastop (2006); it apparently alternates between *Ribes* spp. and several Onagraceae in its area of origin.

Material Examined: AZORES – A1055, 1 aptera, 1 aptera nymph, ex. *Oenothera stricta* (Onagraceae), Aeroporto, Pico, 28.vi.2012, *M. Khadem* leg.

Illinoia lambersi (MacGillivray, 1960)

Already known in Macaronesia from Madeira (Aguiar & Ilharco, 2001), but not present in mainland Portugal. This is a common pest on young leaves, shoots and flowers of rhododendrons. Described from western North America, but introduced to Europe (UK, Denmark, Norway, Netherlands, Belgium, Czech Republic, Slovakia) and South America (Chile).

Material Examined: AZORES – A1056, 2 apterae, ex. *Rhododendron* sp. (Ericaceae), Sete Cidades, São Miguel, 30.vi.2012, *M. Khadem* leg.

DREPANOSIPHIDAE

Neophyllaphis podocarpi Takahashi, 1920

This is a new record for Macaronesia, unknown from mainland Portugal. According to Blackman & Eastop (1994) all 17 species of *Neophyllaphis* live on Podocarpaceae and Araucariaceae in the southern hemisphere and mountains of the tropics, extending northward into China and Japan. The Podocarpus Aphid, *N. podocarpi*, originally described from Japan, presents a wider distribution that includes China, Taiwan, Japan, Java, Malaya, Hawaii and Australia. It was introduced in the United States in 1954 (Russell, 1982) and Italy (Limonta, 1990).

Material Examined: AZORES – A998, 4 apterae, ex. *Podocarpus macrophyllus* (Podocarpaceae), Campus da Universidade de Ponta Delgada, São Miguel, 18.ix.2010; A1039, 2 alate, 4 apterae, *Podocarpus macrophyllus* (Podocarpaceae), Campus da Universidade de Ponta Delgada, São Miguel, 20.vi.2012; A1040, 1 aptera, 1 alata nymph, ex. *Podocarpus macrophyllus* (Podocarpaceae), Igreja de Sete Cidades, São Miguel, 21.vi.2012; A1041, 2 apterae, 1 alata, ex. *Podocarpus macrophyllus* (Podocarpaceae), Nordeste, São Miguel, 29.vi.2012; A1042, 2 apterae, 3 nymphs, ex. *Podocarpus macrophyllus* (Podocarpaceae), Igreja de Sete Cidades, São Miguel, 30.vi.2012; A1043, 3 alate, 1 alata nymph, ex. *Podocarpus macrophyllus* (Podocarpaceae), Furnas, São Miguel, 1.vii.2012. All samples: *M. Khadem* leg.

Species that have extended their distribution in the Azores Archipelago

APHIDIDAE

Aphis craccivora Koch, 1854

A very common aphid throughout Macaronesia and mainland Portugal.

In the Azores Archipelago it is already known from the islands of Corvo, Flores, Faial, Pico, Terceira, São Miguel and Santa Maria (Pita & Ilharco, 2010). We record it now from São Jorge Island.

Material Examined: AZORES – A1046, 1 aptera, 1 aptera nymph, 1 alata, ex. *Glycine sinensis* (Fabaceae), Fajã das Almas, São Jorge, 23.vi.2012, *M. Khadem* leg.

***Aphis fabae* Scopoli, 1763**

Another extremely common aphid in all Macaronesian Archipelagos and also mainland Portugal. According to Pita & Ilharco (2010) it exists in all Azorean islands except in Pico, where we can now confirm its presence.

Material Examined: AZORES – A1051, 2 apterae, 1 alata nymph, ex. *Banksia integrifolia* (Proteaceae), Ribeiras, Pico, 26.vi.2012; A1052, 3 apterae, ex. *Myrica faya* (Myricaceae), São Roque, Pico, 27.vi.2012. Both samples: *M. Khadem* leg.

***Aphis hederæ* Kalténbach, 1843**

Known from mainland Portugal, in Macaronesia *A. hederæ* is only not listed from the Cape Verde Islands. In the Azores, it has been recorded from: Flores, Faial, São Jorge, Terceira, São Miguel and Santa Maria (Pita & Ilharco, 2010). This is the first record for Pico Island.

Material Examined: AZORES – A1048, 2 apterae, 1 aptera nymph, 1 alata, ex. *Hedera azorica* (Araliaceae), São João, Pico, 26.vi.2012; A1049, 1 aptera, 2 apterae nymphs, ex. *Hedera azorica* (Araliaceae), Ribeiras, Pico, 26.vi.2012; A1050, 3 apterae, ex. *Hedera azorica* (Araliaceae), Madalena, Pico, 27.vi.2012. All samples: *M. Khadem* leg.

***Aphis ruborum* (Börner, 1932)**

This species is also listed from mainland Portugal and all Macaronesian Archipelagos except Cape Verde. In the Azores, according to Pita & Ilharco (2010), it is known from Flores, Faial, Terceira, São Miguel and Santa Maria. Our record is the first for São Jorge Island.

Material Examined: AZORES – A1044, 3 apterae, 1 aptera nymph, ex. *Rubus* sp. (Rosaceae), Ribeira Seca, São Jorge, 22.vi.2012; A1045, 2 apterae, 1 aptera nymph, ex. *Rubus* sp. (Rosaceae), Rosais, São Jorge, 24.vi.2012. Both samples: *M. Khadem* leg.

***Macrosiphum rosæ* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Another species listed from mainland Portugal and all Macaronesia except the Cape Verde Archipelago. The Rose Aphid is known from the Azorean Islands: Corvo, Flores, Faial, Graciosa, Terceira, São Miguel and Santa Maria (Pita & Ilharco, 2010). This is the first record for São Jorge Island.

Material Examined: AZORES – A1047, 1 aptera, 1 aptera nymph, ex. *Rubus* sp. (Rosaceae), Velas, São Jorge, 25.vi.2012, *M. Khadem* leg.

LACHNIDAE

***Cinara pinimaritimæ* (Dufour, 1833)**

In Macaronesia it is already recorded for Madeira, Azores, Canary Islands (Tenerife), but unknown in the Cape Verde Archipelago. In the Azores, according to Pita & Ilharco (2010), it is known from all the

TABLE 2. — THE NUMBER OF APHID SPECIES PER ARCHIPELAGO AND PER ISLAND IN EACH ARCHIPELAGO

Madeira: 183									
Madeira	Porto Santo		Desertas			Selvagens			
			I. Chão	D. Grande	Bugio	S. Grande	S. Pequena	I. Fora	
177	40		1	1	0	7	1	0	
Azores: 151									
Corvo	Flores	Faial	Pico	Graciosa	S. Jorge	Terceira	S. Miguel	S. Maria	
20	86	46	23	18	23	74	130	65	
Canary Islands: 142									
Tenerife	G. Canaria	La Palma	El Hierro	La Gomera	Lanzarote	Fuerteventura			
122	52	65	29	48	18	31			
Cape Verde: 30									
S. Antão		S. Vicente		S. Luzia		Branco		Raso	S. Nicolau
16		1		0		0		0	4
Sal		B. Vista		Maio		Santiago		Fogo	Brava
3		0		1		23		9	0

islands except Pico and São Jorge, from where we now record it as new. It is also known from mainland Portugal.

Material Examined: AZORES – A1053, 1 aptera, ex. *Pinus pinaster* (Pinaceae), Companhia de Cima, Pico, 27.vi.2012; A1054, 2 apterae, ex. *Pinus pinaster* (Pinaceae), Madalena, Pico, 28.vi.2012. Both samples: *M. Khadem* leg.

DISCUSSION

As stated in the introduction, with the new records here reported, the total number of aphid species known from these Archipelagos is now 183 for Madeira and 151 for the Azores. How does this compare with species numbers on the other Macaronesian Archipelagos? According to Oromí, Cruz, & Báez (2010) the number of aphid species recorded on the Canary Islands amounts to 142, and Pérez Hidalgo, Báez & Martín (2005) indicate only 30 aphid species for the Cape Verde Islands. Table 2 summarizes the total number of aphid species per Archipelago and for each of the 36 Macaronesian islands.

Most of the aphid fauna in the Archipelago of Madeira is composed of introduced species (66%), some of them invasive pests like *Toxoptera citricidus*, and 34% can be considered native (Table 3). The percentage of introduced species versus native species is highest in the Azores (75% against 25%), and is almost at equilibrium in the Cape Verde Islands (57% against 43%).

Oromí, Cruz, & Báez (2010) indicate that 94% of the 142 aphid species recorded for the Canary Islands are native to those islands, although most of them are classified by these authors as 'possibly native'. The native aphid fauna of Macaronesia is very poor in endemic species. Cape Verde has no endemic species and the other Archipelagos each have one

TABLE 3. — THE NUMBER OF NATIVE VERSUS INTRODUCED APHID SPECIES ON EACH MACARONESIAN ARCHIPELAGO

	Native	Introduced
Madeira	61	121
Azores	37	113
Canary Islands	134	8
Cape Verde	13	17

endemic taxon: *Macrosiphoniella madeirensis* Aguiar & Ilharco (Madeira), *Acyrtosiphon supranubius* Carnero Hernández & Nieto Nafria (Canary Islands) and *Capitophorus hippophaes dubius* Ilharco (Azores).

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REFERENCES

- Aguiar, A.M.F. & Ilharco, F.A.**, 2001, Aphids (Homoptera: Aphidoidea) from Madeira Island – new records and corrections, *Boletim de Sanidad Vegetal – Plagas*, **27**(3): 323–336.
- 2008, Hemiptera – Sternorrhyncha (Aphidoidea, Phylloxeroidea), pp. 304–307. *In*: Borges, P.A.V., Abreu, C., Aguiar, A.M.F., Carvalho, P., Jardim, R., Melo, I., Oliveira, P., Sérgio, C., Serrano, A.R.M., & Vieira, P. (Eds), *A list of the terrestrial fungi, flora and fauna of Madeira and Selvagens Archipelagos*, Funchal & Angra do Heroísmo: DRAmb, Madeira & Universidade dos Açores.
- Aguiar, A.M.F., Pita, M.T. & Ilharco, F.A.**, 1995, Additions to the aphid fauna (Homoptera: Aphidoidea) of the Archipelago of Madeira, pp. 191–201. *In*: Comité Editorial (Eds), *Avances en Entomologia Ibérica*, Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales, y Univ. Autónoma de Madrid.
- Alford, D.V.**, 1984, *A colour atlas of fruit pests – their recognition, biology and control*, London: Wolfe Publishing.
- Andrada, E.C.**, 1990, *Reposoamento florestal no Arquipélago da Madeira (1952–1975)*, Lisboa: Ministério da Agricultura, Pescas e Alimentação.
- Barbagallo, S. & Stroyan, H.L.G.**, 1982, Osservazioni biologiche, ecologiche e tassonomiche sull'afidofauna della Sicilia, *Frustula Entomologica* (N.S.), **3**: 1–182 (1980).
- Beardsley, J.W. Jr.**, 1979, The current status of the names of Hawaiian aphids (Homoptera: Aphididae), *Proceedings, Hawaiian Entomological Society*, **13**(1): 45–50.
- Bella, S., Mifsud, D., Pérez Hidalgo, N. & Barbagallo, S.**, 2009, *Greenidea ficicola*: is it an example of rapid colonization due to climatic changes? 8th International Symposium on Aphids, Catania (Italy), 8–12 June 2009.
- Ben Halima-Kamel, M.**, 2009, First report of *Greenidea ficicola* in Tunisia, *Tunisian Journal of Plant Protection*, **4**(1): 107–110.
- Blackman, R.L.**, 2013, Aphids on the world's plants – An online identification and information guide, <http://www.aphidsontheworldsplants.info> [accessed 07/08/2013].

- Blackman, R.L. & Eastop, V.F.**, 1989, *Aphids on the world's crops – an identification guide*, London: Wiley, Interscience publication.
- 1994, *Aphids on the world's trees – an identification and information guide*, London: CAB International.
- 2006, *Aphids on the world's herbaceous plants and shrubs, vol. 1: host lists and keys; vol. 2: the aphids*, West Sussex: Wiley.
- Boukhris-Bouhachem, S., Souissi, R., Turpeau, E., Rouzé-Jouan, J., Fahem, M. Brahim, N.B. & Hullé, M.**, 2007, Aphid (Hemiptera: Aphidoidea) diversity in Tunisia in relation to seed potato production, *Annales de la Société Entomologique Française (n.s.)*, **43**(3): 311–318.
- Ciesla, W.M.**, 1991, Cypress aphid, *Cinara cupressi*, a new pest of conifers in eastern and southern Africa, *FAO Plant Protection Bulletin*, **39**(2–3): 82–93.
- Durak, R.**, 2012, *Cinara fresai* (Blanchard, 1939) (Hemiptera: Aphidoidea) – an aphid species new to Poland, *Wiadomości Entomologiczne*, **31**(2): 73–77.
- Foottit, R.G. & Maw, E.**, 1997, Aphids (Homoptera: Aphidoidea) of the Yukon, pp 387–404. *In*: Danks, H.V. & Downes, J.A. (Eds.), *Insects of the Yukon*. Ottawa: Biological Survey of Canada (Terrestrial Arthropods).
- Foottit, R.G., Halbert, S.E., Miller, G.L., Maw, E. & Russell, L.M.**, 2006, Adventive aphids (Hemiptera: Aphididae) of America North of Mexico, *Proceedings of the Entomological Society of Washington*, **108**(3): 583–610.
- Gomez Menor, J. & Nieto Nafria, J.M.**, 1977, Contribución al conocimiento de los pulgones de España (Hem. Homoptera, Aphidoidea), *Graellsia*, **32**: 227–260.
- Hansen, A. & Sunding, P.**, 1993, Flora of Macaronesia. Checklist of vascular plants 4, revised edition, *Sommerfeltia*, **17**: 1–295.
- Harten, A. van**, 1993, The aphids (Homoptera: Aphidoidea) of the Cape Verde Islands, *Courier Forschungsinstitut Senckenberg*, **159**: 381–385.
- Harten, A. van, Ilharco, F.A. & Prinsen, J.D.**, 1994, *A general guide to the aphids of Yemen*, Sana'a, Yemen: Yemeni German Plant Protection Project.
- Heie, O.E.**, 1975, Notes on some East African aphids (Homoptera, Aphidoidea), *Journal of the East African Natural History Society and National Museum*, **155**: 1–4.
- 1980, The Aphidoidea (Hemiptera) of Fennoscandia and Denmark. I. General Part. The families Mindaridae, Hormaphididae, Thelaxidae, Anoeciidae and Pemphigidae, *Fauna Entomologica Scandinavica*, **9**: 1–236.
- 1986, The Aphidoidea (Hemiptera) of Fennoscandia and Denmark. III. Family Aphididae: subfamily Pterocommatinae & tribe Aphidini of subfamily Aphidinae, *Fauna Entomologica Scandinavica*, **17**: 5–314.
- 1991, The Aphidoidea (Hemiptera) of Fennoscandia and Denmark. IV. Family Aphididae, part 1 of tribe Macrosiphini of subfamily Aphidinae, *Fauna Entomologica Scandinavica*, **25**: 1–189.
- Hržič, A.**, 1996, Opazovanje naleta listnih uši (Aphididae) v letu 1994, *Sodobno kmetijstvo*, **29**(2): 54–56.
- Ilharco, F.A.**, 1973, *Catálogo dos afídeos de Portugal Continental*, Oeiras: Estação Agronómica Nacional.
- 1974, List of the aphids of Madeira Island (Homoptera, Aphidoidea), *Bocagiana*, **35**: 1–44.
- 1976, A first list of the aphids of the Azores (Homoptera, Aphidoidea), *Agronomia Lusitana*, **37**(3): 207–267.
- 1979, 1º aditamento ao Catálogo dos afídeos de Portugal Continental (Homoptera, Aphidoidea), *Agronomia Lusitana*, **39**(4): 253–294.
- 1984, New records to the aphid fauna of the Archipelago of Madeira (Homoptera, Aphidoidea), *Boletim do Museu Municipal do Funchal*, **36**(163): 177–206.
- 1986, Afidofauna madeirense: comentários zoogeográficos (Insecta, Homoptera, Aphidoidea), *Boletim da Sociedade Portuguesa de Entomologia*, **II–14**(44): 149–157 (1984).
- Jardim, R. & Sequeira, M.M.**, 2008, List of vascular plants (Pteridophyta and Spermatophyta), pp. 179–207. *In*: Borges, P.A.V., Abreu, C., Aguiar, A.M.F., Carvalho,

P., Jardim, R., Melo, I., Oliveira, P., Sérgio, C., Serrano, A.R.M. & Vieira, P. (Eds), *A list of the terrestrial fungi, flora and fauna of Madeira and Selvagens archipelagos*, Direcção Regional do Ambiente da Madeira & Universidade dos Açores, Funchal & Angra do Heroísmo.

- Limonta, L.**, 1990, Callaphididae (Aphidoidea) nuovi per l'Italia, *Bollettino di Zoologia Agraria e di Bachicoltura*, **22**(1): 93–99.
- Lowe, A.D.**, 1966, Some records of aphids including six species not previously recorded from New Zealand, *New Zealand Journal of Science*, **9**: 357–360.
- Lowe, S., Browne, M., Boudjelas, S. & De Poorter, M.**, 2000, *100 of the world's worst invasive alien species. A selection from the Global Invasive Species Database*, The Invasive Species Specialist Group (ISSG), a specialist group of the Species Survival Commission (SSC) of the World Conservation Union (IUCN).
- Menezes de Sequeira, M., Jardim, R., Silva, M. & Carvalho, L.**, 2007, *Musschia isambertoi* M. Seq., R. Jardim, M. Silva & L. Carvalho (Campanulaceae), a new species from the Madeira Archipelago (Portugal), *Anales del Jardín Botánico de Madrid*, **64**(2): 135–146.
- Nieto Nafría, J.M.**, 2004, Fauna Europaea: Hemiptera, Aphidoidea, Fauna Europaea version 1.0, 27 September 2004, <http://www.faunaeur.org> [accessed 07/08/2013].
- Nieto, J.M. & Mier, M.**, 1976, Una nueva especie de pulgón: *A. hillerislambersi*, *EOS*, **51**: 69–76 (1975).
- Nieto Nafría, J.M. Mier Durante, M.P. & Carnero Hernández, A.**, 1977, La afidofauna macaronésica, pp. 55–65. In: Nieto Nafría, J.M. Mier Durante, M.P. & Carnero Hernández, A. (Eds), *Estudios afidológicos de las Islas Canarias y de la Macaronesia*, Excelentísimo Cabildo Insular de Tenerife, Aula de Cultura, Salamanca.
- Nieto Nafría, J.M., Mier Durante, M.P., García Prieto, F. & Pérez Hidalgo, N.**, 2005, Hemiptera, Aphididae III. In: *Fauna Iberica*, vol. 28, Ramos, M.A. et al. (Eds), Madrid: Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales, CSIC.
- Oromí, P., Cruz, S. & Báez, M.**, 2010, Hemiptera, Aphididae, pp. 235–238, In: Arechavaleta, M., Rodríguez, S., Zurita, N. & García, A. (Eds), *Lista de especies silvestres de Canarias. Hongos, plantas y animales terrestres*. 2009, Gobierno de Canarias.
- Ortego, J. Pérez Hidalgo, N., Nieto Nafría, J.M. & Mier Durante, M.P.**, 2006, Six alien aphid species (Hemiptera: Aphididae) recorded for the first time from South America, *Florida Entomologist*, **89** (2): 111–116.
- Palma, A. & Rei, F.T.**, 1999, Estudos em variedades não remontantes de *Rubus idaeus* L. no âmbito da protecção integrada da cultura contra pragas, pp. 367–375. In: *Actas do V Encontro Nacional de Protecção Integrada*, Bragança.
- Pérez Hidalgo, N., Báez, M. & Martín, E.**, 2005, Hemiptera, Aphididae, p. 72. In: Arechavaleta, M., Zurita, N., Marrero, M.C. & Martín, J.L. (Eds), *Lista preliminar de especies silvestres de Cabo Verde (hongos, plantas y animales terrestres*, Consejería de Medio Ambiente y Ordenación Territorial, Gobierno de Canarias.
- Pita, M.T. & Ilharco, F.A.**, 1997, Additions to the aphid fauna of the Azores (Homoptera: Aphidoidea), *Boletim do Museu Municipal do Funchal*, **49**(274): 77–88.
- 2004a, Azorean aphid fauna (Homoptera, Aphidoidea): comments on some species and an updated list, *Boletim de Sanidad Vegetal, Plagas*, **30**: 301–310.
- 2004b, Aphid fauna of Madeira Archipelago and Salvage Islands: new records and updated list (Homoptera, Aphidoidea), *Vieraea*, **32**: 49–61.
- 2005, Hemiptera – Sternorrhyncha (Aphidoidea), pp. 194–197. In: Borges, P.A.V., Cunha, R., Gabriel, R., Martins, A.F., Silva, L. & Vieira, V. (Eds), *A list of the terrestrial fauna (Mollusca and Arthropoda) and flora (Bryophyta, Pteridophyta and Spermatophyta) from the Azores*, Direcção Regional do Ambiente and Universidade dos Açores, Horta, Angra do Heroísmo and Ponta Delgada.
- 2010, Hemiptera – Sternorrhyncha (Aphidoidea), pp. 219–221. In: Borges, P.A.V., Costa, A., Cunha, R., Gabriel, R., Gonçalves, V., Martins, A.F., Melo, I., Parente, M., Raposeiro, P., Rodrigues, P., Santos, R.S., Silva, L., Vieira, P. & Vieira, V. (Eds), *A list of the terrestrial and marine biota from the Azores*, Cascais: Principia.

- Quirós, D.I., Remaudière, G. & Nieto Nafria, J.M.**, 2009, Contribución al conocimiento de Aphididae y Phylloxeridae (Hemiptera: Sternorrhyncha) de Panamá, *Neotropical Entomology*, **38**(6): 791–800.
- Remaudière, G., Nieto Nafria, J.M. & Mier Durante, M.P.**, 1986, Nuevas aportaciones al conocimiento de la fauna española de pulgones (Hom., Aphidoidea), *Boletín de la Asociación Española de Entomología*, **10**: 313–333.
- Rodrigues, P.M.C.**, 2004, *Inimigos naturais e dinâmica de infestação de afídeos (Hemiptera, Aphidoidea), em pomares de limoeiro, com diferentes modalidades de gestão da flora adventícia*, Relatório do Trabalho de Fim de Curso de Engenharia Agronómica, Lisboa: Instituto Superior de Agronomia.
- Rodrigues, P., Ilharco, F.A., Silva, E.B. & Franco, J.C.**, 2006, Interactions between ground cover management, hedges and aphids in lemon orchards, *Integrated Control in Citrus Fruit Crops, IOBC wprs Bulletin*, **29**(3): 117–125.
- Rubin de Celis, V.E., Ortiz, M.S. & Barletta, C.F.**, 2006, *Greenidea ficicola* Takahashi (Hemiptera: Aphididae) nuevo registro para Sudamérica, *Revista peruana de Entomología*, **45**: 105–107.
- Russell, L.**, 1982, The genus *Neophyllaphis* and its species (Hemiptera: Homoptera: Aphididae), *Florida Entomologist*, **65**(4): 538–573.
- Sano, M. & Matsumoto, Y.**, 2005, Occurrence of *Aloephagus myersi* (Aphididae) in Japan, *Biogeography*, **7**: 29–30.
- Sérgio, C., Sim-Sim, M., Fontinha, S. & Figueira, R.**, 2008, List of Bryophytes (Bryophyta), pp. 143–156. In: Borges, P.A.V., Abreu, C., Aguiar, A.M.F., Carvalho, P., Jardim, R., Melo, I., Oliveira, P., Sérgio, C., Serrano, A.R.M. & Vieira, P. (Eds), *A list of the terrestrial fungi, flora and fauna of Madeira and Selvagens archipelagos*, Direcção Regional do Ambiente da Madeira & Universidade dos Açores, Funchal & Angra do Heroísmo.
- Shaposhnikov, G.K.**, 1964, Suborder Aphidinea – plant lice, pp. 616–799. In: Bei-Bienko, G.Y., *Keys to the insects of the European USSR*, vol. 1.
- Sousa-Silva, C.R. & Ilharco, F.A.**, 2001, First report of *Cinara cupressi* (Lachninae: Cinarini) in Brazil, *Revista de Biologia Tropical*, **49**(2): 768.
- Sousa-Silva, C.R., Brombal, J.C. & Ilharco, F.A.**, 2005, *Greenidia ficicola* Takahashi (Hemiptera: Greenideidae), a new aphid in Brazil, *Neotropical Entomology*, **34**(6): 1023–1024.
- Tavares, J.S.**, 1903, Primeira contribuição para o estudo das zoocécidas da Ilha da Madeira, *Broteria*, **2**: 179–186.
- Tizado Morales, E.J. & Nieto Nafria, J.M.**, 1994, A new species of *Uroleucon* (Hom. Aphididae) on *Andryala* spp.: a multivariate analysis, *The Canadian Entomologist*, **126**: 1251–1261.
- Tsitsipis, J.A., Katis, N.I., Margaritopoulos, J.T., Lykouressis, D.P., Avgelis, A.D., Gargalianou, J., Zarpas, K.D., Perdakis, D.C. & Papapanayotou, A.**, 2007, A contribution to the aphid fauna of Greece, *Bulletin of Insectology*, **60**(1): 31–38.
- Tuatay, N.**, 1999, Türkiye Yaprakbitleri (Homoptera: Aphididae) V. Chaitophorinae, Lachninae ve Thelaxinae, *Bitki Koruma Bülteni*, **39**(1–2): 1–21.
- Vieira, R.M.S.**, 2002, Flora da Madeira – plantas vasculares naturalizadas no Arquipélago da Madeira, *Boletim do Museu Municipal do Funchal (História Natural)*, Supl. No. **8**: 1–281.

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